

Oxidation of Hydrocarbons with Quinquevalent Vanadium

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Kinetics of oxidation of diphenyl methane, triphenyl methane, fluorene and cyclohexane by Vanadium V in aqueous acetic acid medium are reported. The experimental findings are rationalised on the basis of previously postulated mechanism.

In continuation of our work already reported on toluene, nitrotoluenes, methoxy toluenes and halogenated toluenes by Vanadium V¹⁻⁵, we report now some features of this process with diphenyl methane, triphenyl methane and fluorene.

EXPERIMENTAL

The substrates used are of guaranteed quality or purified by the usual procedures wherever necessary.

Vanadium V solutions were prepared and kinetics was followed by the method described earlier (*loc. cit.*).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reactions are second order reactions, first order in the substrate and first order in the oxidant. The Zucker-Hammett slope is 2.0 for diphenyl methane and fluorene. We have already reported that dependence on acidity seems to be dependent on the nature of the substrate. Such a finding finds support from the observations of Ross Stewart. Experimental conditions in the work on oxidation of aliphatic secondary alcohols by Chromium VI in strong sulphuric acid solutions is quite comparable to the conditions of these experiments⁶.

TABLE I

<i>Temperature 60°</i> Solvent—70% aqueous acetic acid <i>Substrate</i>	<i>Acidity -8.1 N(H₂SO₄)</i> $10^2 \times k \text{ l. moles}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
Toluene (b.p. 110.5°)	34.46
Diphenyl methane (b.p. 265°)	157.4
Triphenyl methane (m.p. 93.4°)	190.0
Cyclohexane (b.p. 80.7)	1.209

1. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, *Chem. and Ind.* (London), 1966, 1722.
2. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 640.
3. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, Part III of the proceedings of the 54th Session, Indian Science Congress, 1967, p. 95.
4. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.* (India), (in press).
5. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, Part III of the proceedings of the 55th Session, Indian Science Congress, 1968, p. 108.
6. Donald G. Lee and Ross Stewart, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 2868.

TABLE II

<i>Temperature</i> 60°	<i>Substrate—Diphenyl methane</i>
Solvent—70% aqueous acetic acid	
<i>Acidity</i> (H ₂ SO ₄)	10 ² × <i>k</i> 1.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
6.3 N	11.52
7.2 N	45.00
8.1 N	157.40

TABLE III

<i>Temperature</i> 60°	<i>Substrate—Fluorene</i> (m.p. 115.5°)
Solvent—70% aqueous acetic acid	
<i>Acidity</i> (H ₂ SO ₄)	10 ² × <i>k</i> 1.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
2.7 N	93.84
3.6 N	481.80

The tables indicate that the order of the reactivity is fluorene > triphenyl methane > diphenyl methane > toluene > cyclohexane. The reaction is very fast with fluorene and hence lower acidity conditions have been chosen. The position 9 in fluorene is very labile and hence easy oxidation takes place. Even though fluorene can give rise to binuclear oxidation products, under the conditions of the present experiments no indication of the formation of such compounds was noticed. It is clear that the incipient carbonium ion that will be formed because of the expulsion of the hydride anion is stabilized maximum in fluorene and hence of high reactivity. Resonance factors are playing a dominant role in these reactions. The trend of observed reactivity is justifiable but the extent to which triphenyl methane is reacting faster over diphenyl methane seems to call for explanation. It may be recalled that we postulated that the reaction passes through the following transition state:

on the basis of a high ρ value (-3.75) and a low ω value (+0.3162) and three fold acceleration observed with Mn⁺⁺ in our work with toluenes. It can be seen that the back side displacement by water seems to be hindered by the three aryl groups as the mechanism postulated is an S_N2 process bordering S_N1 character. Another explanation may be seen in the product stability. In the case of fluorene and diphenyl methane, the products are ketones which are stabilized by conjugation influences more than the parent hydrocarbons. In the case of triphenyl methane the product is triphenyl methanol which has no such carbonyl stabilization with π bonded aromatic system. Hence the reactivity is not so pronounced in the case of triphenyl methane. The most sluggish system seems to be cyclohexane, which is an alicyclic system which has no resonance stabilization like others. The species has been mentioned as VO₂⁺ only for convenience, it may be actually any one of the sulphate complexes as postulated by Waters⁷.